

Proof, Attitudes, and Gender: A Study in Early Math Education

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Abstract

This study examines the attitudes of undergraduate mathematics students (N = 267) towards mathematical proving during an introductory proof course situated at the beginning of their academic curriculum. Over one term, four attitude variables self-efficacy, anxiety, appreciation, and motivation—were measured using a newly developed self-report instrument based on existing frameworks for mathematics attitudes and proof-related self-efficacy.

The findings reveal significant relationships between students' prior performance and their proof-related self-efficacy, anxiety, and motivation at the start of the course. Female students reported lower self-efficacy and motivation compared to male students, a disparity that persisted throughout the course. The course positively impacted attitudes, with students experiencing an increase in self-efficacy and a reduction in anxiety. High motivation at the start of the course emerged as a strong predictor of success in the final course project.

These results highlight the importance of addressing students' attitudes towards proving in the design of introductory courses, as these attitudes can significantly influence their academic performance. Additionally, the study underscores the need to consider and address gender-related disparities to ensure an equitable learning environment in mathematics education.

Introduction

Proving plays a central role in mathematics, serving as a means to validate results, derive new findings, and communicate reasoning within the mathematical community. In education, proofs are integral to teaching key mathematical strategies and concepts (Hanna & Barbeau, 2010). As a result, proving is emphasized in university-level mathematics. However, at the pre-university level, proving is often limited to specific areas, such as geometry, and is rarely a focus in general curricula (Furinghetti et al., 2011; Mingus & Grassl, 1999; Hibi, 2021a; Hibi, 2021d; Hibi, 2022b; Hibi, 2024d). This lack of exposure contributes to students' widespread difficulty with proving, which is considered one of the most challenging aspects of mathematics (Moore, 1994). The transition to proof-based learning at university is particularly demanding for many students (Selden, 2012). Research on mathematical proof has addressed various aspects, including construction, validation, and interpretation (Alcock & Weber, 2010; Hodds et al., 2014; Selden & Selden, 2009). Additionally, studies have examined students' beliefs about proofs (Almeida, 2000; Conner et al., 2011) and pre-service teachers' perspectives on teaching proof (Lesseig & Hine, 2022; Schwarz et al., 2008; Hibi, 2024c). Despite this, the affective dimensions of proving—such as emotions, attitudes, and beliefs—remain underexplored in the literature, even though they are widely acknowledged as significant factors in broader mathematics education research.

Attitudes, defined here as persistent affective dispositions or beliefs that evoke emotions and influence behavior (Leder, 1987; McLeod, 1992), have been extensively studied in mathematics education, particularly in relation to enjoyment, appreciation, and self-confidence (Di Martino & Zan, 2015; Hannula, 2002; Leder, 1987; McLeod, 1992). These attitudes are recognized as predictors of study behaviors and academic performance (Singh et al., 2002; Hibi, 2021b). For instance, higher self-efficacy positively affects mathematical achievement (Pajares & Kranzler, 1995), as does perceiving mathematics as valuable and relevant (Greene et al., 1999).

Gender differences in attitudes toward mathematics are well-documented, with female students often exhibiting lower self-confidence, higher anxiety, and reduced motivation compared to male students (Frost et al., 1994; Hembree, 1990; Middleton & Spanias, 1999). These disparities negatively impact performance and contribute to the underrepresentation of women in STEM fields (Betz & Hackett, 1983; Frost et al., 1994; Hibi, 2021c; Hibi, 2022a).

This study focuses on the affective dimensions of proving, specifically self-efficacy, anxiety, appreciation, and motivation, which are hypothesized to play a critical role in learning proof during the transition to university mathematics. Confidence in one's abilities, motivation, and recognizing the value of proof are crucial for overcoming the challenges of proving. Exploring the relationships between these attitudes, gender, and

performance aims to address existing gaps in the literature and provide new insights into the interplay of affective and cognitive factors in learning proof.

Aim of the study:

This study explored undergraduate students' attitudes towards proving over the course of a 14-week introductory mathematics program. The aim was to examine how these attitudes evolve during the course and how they influence performance, with attention to the role of prior achievement and gender. This initial investigation focuses on a single educational context, providing a foundation for broader future research.

To measure attitudes, we developed an instrument combining two validated questionnaires: The Attitudes Toward Mathematics Inventory (ATMI; Tapia, 1996) and the Proof Self-Efficacy questionnaire (PSE; Iannone & Inglis, 2010). The ATMI was selected for its brevity and its focus on key constructs such as confidence, anxiety, value, enjoyment, and motivation, all of which are relevant to proving. The PSE was included to ensure the instrument's specificity to proving. From these, we constructed a tool assessing four attitude dimensions: self-efficacy, anxiety, appreciation, and motivation.

The study began by investigating students' initial attitudes upon entering university. Previous research demonstrates that prior mathematical achievement correlates with self-efficacy beliefs, anxiety, and motivation (Sitzmann & Yeo, 2013; Ma & Kishor, 1997; Ho et al., 2000; Miller & Bichsel, 2004; Middleton & Spanias, 1999; Murayama et al., 2013; Singh et al., 2002). Gender differences in mathematical attitudes, well-documented in the literature (e.g., Frost et al., 1994; Lahdenperä, 2018; Leder, 1995; Middleton & Spanias, 1999; Wigfield & Meece, 1988), are likely to extend to proving. This led to the first research question: Q1. How are students' attitudes towards proving related to their gender and high school mathematics performance at the beginning of university studies?

The course under investigation was designed to facilitate the transition to university-level mathematics, with a significant focus on mathematical proof. It was hypothesized that the course would positively influence students' attitudes towards proving, potentially reducing gender disparities. To examine this, pre- and post-course surveys were compared to address the second research question:

Q2. How did students' attitudes towards proving change during the course, and what effect did gender have on the change?

Finally, we explored whether attitudes towards proving had a direct impact on students' performance in proof-related tasks. The final project, which included proof-intensive assignments, provided a basis for assessing the relationship between initial attitudes and performance, while controlling for prior mathematical achievement. This analysis addressed the third research question:

Q3. How do differences in attitudes towards proving affect performance in proof-related tasks?

For this question, we also examined gender-specific variations, aiming to understand how attitudinal differences may influence male and female students' performance in proving. This study sheds light on the interplay between attitudes, gender, and achievement, offering insights into how mathematical proving can be more effectively taught in diverse educational contexts.

Theoretical Framework

Attitudes and their measurement in mathematics education:

Attitudes in the context of learning are understood as relatively stable predispositions shaped by prior experiences, which evoke emotional responses toward a subject, reflect beliefs and values about it, and potentially influence behavior (cf. Leder, 1987; McLeod, 1992; Hibi, 2024a; Hibi, 2024b). For instance, a learner may dislike geometry, perceive algebra as unengaging, or value mathematics as essential for career aspirations. Unlike transient emotions such as frustration after failing an exam, attitudes represent a more enduring construct. Additionally, while beliefs might be purely cognitive, such as thinking mathematics is vital for engineering, attitudes are inherently multidimensional and incorporate emotional components. Typically categorized as positive or negative, attitudes are often simplistically described as either favorable or unfavorable; however, we consider them as more complex constructs with distinct dimensions.

Historically, attitudes have been situated within the affective domain, which encompasses psychological processes beyond pure cognition. In mathematics education, McLeod (1992) proposed a tripartite model of affect, comprising beliefs, attitudes, and emotions as key components. This model was later expanded by DeBellis and Goldin (2006) to include values. Despite its significance, clear distinctions between these constructs remain elusive, with overlapping definitions complicating theoretical clarity (Di Martino & Zan, 2011). Leder (1987) highlighted the challenges of comprehensively defining attitudes, while Hannula (2002) characterized them as behaviors shaped by evaluative processes driven by emotions, expectations, and values during learning. Di Martino and Zan (2010), using a grounded theory approach, identified three dimensions of attitude: emotional disposition (e.g., like or dislike), perception of mathematics' value and utility, and perceived competence in relation to self-beliefs.

Beyond theoretical considerations, numerous efforts have been made to measure attitudes toward mathematics. Various self-report instruments have been developed, often incorporating beliefs, values, and emotions that do not align strictly with theoretical definitions of attitude (Di Martino & Zan, 2015; Leder, 1985; Hibi, 2022). Despite conceptual mismatches, such instruments can yield valuable insights if they are valid, reliable, and grounded in an appropriate conceptual framework (Leder, 1985). Historically, measurement of attitudes was motivated by their presumed predictive relationship with achievement, as suggested by Aiken (1970, cited in Di Martino & Zan, 2015). However, a meta-analysis by Ma and Kishor (1997) indicated that the overall effect size of this relationship is minimal and holds limited implications for educational practice.

One of the earliest and most influential tools for measuring attitudes was developed by Fennema and Sherman (1976), which assessed nine dimensions, including confidence, anxiety, active involvement, perceived usefulness, and the influence of parents and teachers. This instrument targeted middle and high school students and framed attitudes as multi-faceted constructs. Subsequently, Tapia and Marsh (Tapia & Marsh, 2002; Tapia, 1996) refined the approach for high school and university students, creating the Attitudes toward Mathematics Inventory (ATMI). This shorter tool focused on four dimensions: sense of security (later termed self-confidence), value, enjoyment, and motivation. Sense of security combined self-efficacy and anxiety, while value referred to the perceived personal utility of mathematics. Enjoyment measured positive anticipations, and motivation reflected the willingness to engage with mathematical tasks. This refined instrument forms the basis of the attitudinal measurements employed in the current study, offering a concise yet robust framework to explore learners' attitudes toward mathematics.

Mathematical proving and attitudes:

Given the importance of attitudes in mathematics learning, it is reasonable to assume that they also influence the learning of proof. Stylianou et al. (2015) examined students' perspectives on the meaning of proof and its connections to their attitudes, beliefs, and experiences. Their study, which included 535 students across six universities, revealed that high-performing students exhibited a greater appreciation for proofs and held more positive beliefs about their abilities as proof learners compared to their lower-performing peers. Similarly, Furinghetti and Morselli (2007, 2009) qualitatively explored the interplay between affect and cognition during the proving processes of university students. Their findings suggest that emotional factors can serve as either facilitators or obstacles in proof construction, highlighting the intertwined nature of affective and cognitive processes in mathematical reasoning.

Iannone and Inglis (2010) developed a questionnaire to measure students' proof-related self-efficacy, which refers to their confidence in their ability to construct proofs. By administering this tool to 76 first-year university students in the UK, they found a positive correlation between students' self-efficacy and their actual performance on proof tasks. Similarly, Viholainen et al. (2019) investigated proof-related self-efficacy among 29 Israel and Swedish undergraduate mathematics students. While students expressed high levels of motivation toward proofs, they also reported self-doubt regarding their proving skills. Factors such as difficulty in managing the proving process and fear of making errors contributed to their low self-efficacy.

Selden and Selden (2013) proposed that self-efficacy is crucial for sustaining persistence in proof construction. They argue that experiencing success in writing proofs can enhance students' self-efficacy, creating a reinforcing cycle where confidence promotes continued effort and improvement in proving abilities. These studies collectively emphasize the critical role of self-efficacy, motivation, and emotional regulation in supporting students' engagement and success in the proving process.

Background for attitude variables used in this study:

The current study used a newly developed instrument to measure attitudes, drawing upon and adapting components from the ATMI (Tapia, 1996) and PSE (Iannone & Inglis, 2010) frameworks. This instrument assesses four key attitudinal variables—self-efficacy, anxiety, appreciation, and motivation—which are integral to understanding students' experiences with mathematical proving. Each variable is grounded in established literature and offers unique insights into the interplay between affective and cognitive dimensions in proof-related learning.

Self-efficacy refers to students' belief in their ability to prove or learn proofs effectively. Rooted in Bandura's (1977) work, self-efficacy is closely related to constructs like "confidence in learning mathematics" (Fennema & Sherman, 1976). Extensive research has shown that self-efficacy is a strong predictor of academic performance (Bandura & Schunk, 1981; Zimmerman, 2000), influencing activity choices, effort, persistence, and emotional responses (Pajares & Graham, 1999). In the context of mathematical proving, self-efficacy has been linked to performance (Iannone & Inglis, 2010). Gender differences are consistently observed, with women often reporting lower self-efficacy than men (Betz & Hackett, 1983; Arens et al., 2022; Hibi, 2024a). Bandura (1997) attributes self-efficacy development to prior achievements, observational learning, social persuasion, and emotional states, all of which shape students' confidence in their proving abilities.

Anxiety, in the context of proving, manifests as tension that disrupts the ability to engage in proving tasks. It parallels mathematics anxiety, which has been negatively correlated with performance across all educational levels (Ma & Kishor, 1997; Miller & Bichsel, 2004). The relationship between anxiety and performance is

complex, with evidence of bidirectional influence (Carey et al., 2016). Anxiety is inversely linked to self-efficacy; students with lower self-efficacy tend to report higher anxiety (Pajares & Kranzler, 1995). Gender disparities are evident, with women generally experiencing higher levels of mathematics anxiety than men (Devine et al., 2012).

Appreciation captures the perceived value of proof, encompassing both its utility in developing reasoning skills and its intrinsic worth. This construct aligns with the notion of "usefulness" in the Fennema–Sherman instrument (Fennema & Sherman, 1976) and features prominently in expectancy-value theories of motivation (Eccles et al., 1983). Prior studies suggest that appreciation for mathematics, including proof, predicts achievement (Greene et al., 1999), with higher-performing students often assigning greater value to proofs than their peers (Stylianou et al., 2015; Hibi, 2024b). Gender-related findings on appreciation remain inconsistent (Gaspard et al., 2015).

Motivation, as explored in this study, reflects a predominantly emotional disposition characterized by an intrinsic desire to engage with proving tasks. It draws on concepts such as intrinsic motivation (Deci & Ryan, 1985) and effectance motivation (White, 1959), emphasizing enjoyment and the drive to overcome challenges. Motivation has a bidirectional relationship with achievement; perceptions of success enhance motivation, which in turn predicts further achievement (Middleton & Spanias, 1999; Singh et al., 2002). Notably, motivation towards mathematics stabilizes during middle school years but can be influenced through thoughtful instructional strategies. Persistent gender gaps in motivation have been documented, with girls often displaying lower motivation to engage with mathematics (Middleton & Spanias, 1999).

This study builds upon these theoretical foundations to explore the nuanced roles of self-efficacy, anxiety, appreciation, and motivation in shaping students' engagement and performance in mathematical proving, with particular attention to gender-based differences.

Design and methods

Context

The study was conducted within the undergraduate course *Introduction to University Mathematics* at an Arab-Israeli academic college. In Israel higher education, students declare a specific major upon entering university, which they focus on throughout their studies, while also selecting one or more minors. Participants in this course included students majoring in mathematics, as well as those pursuing minors in mathematics alongside majors in subjects such as computer science, economics, statistics, or education. The course, typically the first university-level mathematics experience for students, spanned one semester and was worth 5 ECTS credits. Its primary objective was to facilitate the transition from secondary to tertiary mathematics education. Key topics included sets, functions, logic, and proving, with a strong emphasis on the latter. Students practiced various proving techniques, including direct proofs, equivalence proofs, indirect proofs, and mathematical induction. Many participants simultaneously enrolled in other proof-intensive mathematics courses. The course was extensive, involving 600 students who actively engaged by completing at least one assignment.

The course adopted a student-centered learning environment, employing the Extreme Apprenticeship method (Rämö et al., 2019, 2021), a variant of inquiry-based mathematics education (Artigue & Blomhøj, 2013; Laursen & Rasmussen, 2019; Hibi, 2024c). Students began by engaging with course materials and completing computer-based introductory tasks that provided instant feedback. These tasks were inspired by proof frameworks (Selden et al., 2018), which clarify the relationship between the logical structure of a mathematical statement and the corresponding proof. Following this, students advanced to more complex pen-and-paper tasks, deepening their understanding.

Every two weeks, one pen-and-paper task was evaluated by the teaching team, which consisted of a lead instructor and tutors who were undergraduate or graduate students. The team met weekly to discuss both mathematical and pedagogical issues. They provided students with feedback on their submissions, allowing revisions and resubmissions. An open learning space was available for students to collaborate, seek assistance, and engage with the materials at their own pace. Lectures aimed to motivate topics, create a cohesive understanding of key ideas, and connect different concepts. Students were encouraged to share ideas, regardless of correctness, fostering an open and supportive learning atmosphere.

The course concluded with a final project, a comprehensive assignment emphasizing proof construction and clear mathematical communication. Students had three weeks to complete the project, working collaboratively but submitting individual work. The assignment required explaining concepts in their own words, applying unfamiliar mathematical ideas, and constructing original proofs, ensuring the work could not be directly copied. The project accounted for 15% of the course grade, with the remainder determined by weekly tasks. This structure promoted a balance of individual effort, collaborative learning, and sustained engagement with mathematical proving.

Participants

The participants in this study were students enrolled in the course *Introduction to University Mathematics*, who completed digital surveys during the course and provided informed consent for their responses to be used in research. The responses from all participants were initially utilized to develop the attitude survey instrument, as

detailed in the following section. Out of the total course participants, 535 students (89%) responded to the pre-course questionnaire, and 440 students (73%) completed the post-course questionnaire.

For the primary analysis, the participant pool was refined for several reasons. First, only students who completed both the pre- and post-course questionnaires were included to enable analysis of changes in attitude variables (Q1). Second, only those who identified their gender as either female or male were included, as these were the only sufficiently large groups for meaningful statistical analysis of gender-based differences (Q2). Third, participants were required to have taken the advanced mathematics syllabus in their high school matriculation examination and to have reported their final grade in the questionnaire. This was necessary to include the high school final examination grade as a control variable. Finally, only students who submitted the final project for the course were included to facilitate the investigation of the relationship between attitude variables and performance outcomes (Q3).

After applying these criteria, the final sample for the main analysis comprised 267 students (120 females, 147 male), representing 45% of the total course participants.

Data collection and factor analysis

Data was collected from participants through digital self-report surveys administered at the start and end of the focus course, specifically in September and December 2019. Attitudinal data were gathered using a combined questionnaire based on two established Likert scale instruments: The Attitudes Toward Mathematics Inventory (ATMI) (Tapia, 1996) and the Proof Self-Efficacy (PSE) scale (Iannone & Inglis, 2010). The ATMI instrument assesses four dimensions of mathematical attitudes: "sense of security," "value," "motivation," and "enjoyment," using 40 items rated on a 5-point Likert scale. The PSE scale evaluates self-efficacy in proving through 10 items, also on a 5-point scale.

Both instruments were translated into Israel by one of the authors, with ATMI items reworded to reference proving instead of mathematics. For example, the statement "I believe studying mathematics helps me with problem solving in other areas" was modified to "I believe that studying proofs helps me with problem solving in other areas." Items in ATMI that could not be adapted meaningfully were excluded. The final questionnaire comprised 46 items presented in randomized order, retaining the original 5-point response scale ranging from "I strongly disagree" to "I strongly agree." The same set of questions was used in both pre- and post-course surveys.

Given that the combined questionnaire integrated two distinct instruments—one specific to proving and neither previously used in the Israel context—a factor analysis was conducted to identify the underlying dimensions and validate the items. The analysis was performed on the pre-course survey using R software (R Core Team, 2020) and the "psych" package (Revelle, 2020). Responses were treated as continuous, and Pearson correlation coefficients were used, following recommendations by Rhemtulla et al. (2012). Factors were extracted using the maximum likelihood method, with an oblique promax rotation applied due to assumed non-zero correlations between attitude dimensions (Costello & Osborne, 2005).

The number of factors was determined using a scree plot and parallel analysis of eigenvalues. After ensuring the distinctiveness and coherence of the suggested factors, a four-factor solution was selected. Items were then refined to achieve a simple structure, retaining only those with factor loadings above 0.6. Items with cross-loadings that contradicted their original thematic context were removed. For instance, an ATMI item originally reflecting "enjoyment" loaded onto a factor associated with "sense of security" and "self-efficacy." Such inconsistencies were attributed to poor wording or translation, leading to their exclusion. To maintain consistency, each factor was reduced to six items with the highest loadings. Final factor loadings are detailed in Table 8 in the Appendix.

The same factor analysis was applied to the post-course questionnaire to confirm the reliability of the factor structure. All retained items loaded onto the same factors as in the pre-course analysis, validating the structure. Average scores for each factor were calculated for use in subsequent analyses.

Factors were named based on their original categorizations and the thematic interpretation of retained items. The first factor, comprising all PSE items and some ATMI "sense of security" items, was named Self-Efficacy. The second factor, containing negatively coded ATMI "sense of security" items, was named Anxiety. The third factor, including only ATMI "value" items, was named Appreciation. The final factor, combining ATMI "enjoyment" and "motivation" items, was named Motivation. Examples and origins of items for each factor are presented in Table 1, with the full item set detailed in Table 9 in the Appendix.

Table 1: The Four Attitude Variables: Self-efficacy, Anxiety, Appreciation, and Motivation Sources and example items used in the final instrument

Variable	Source	Example Items (translated from Israel)
Self-efficacy	ATMI 'sense of security,' PSE (self-efficacy)	PSE4: I am good at writing mathematical proofs SEC13: I believe that I am good at proving-related tasks
Anxiety	ATMI 'sense of security,' negatively coded	SEC12: Studying proofs makes me feel nervous SEC6: Proofs make me feel uncomfortable
Appreciation	ATMI 'value'	VAL10: I believe that studying proofs helps me with

		problem-solving in other areas
		VAL6: Strong skills in proving can help me in working life
Motivation	ATMI 'motivation,' 'enjoyment'	MOT3: The challenge of proving appeals to me
		ENJ4: I like solving new proving-related problems

Main analyses

The main analyses in this study were conducted using R software (R Core Team, 2020) with the assistance of the "rstatix" package (Kassambara, 2020). To explore the relationship between high school grades and the attitudinal variables at the start of the course, four linear regression analyses were performed, treating the attitudes (self-efficacy, anxiety, appreciation, and motivation) as dependent variables and high school grades as the independent variable. To ensure comparability, we examined gender differences in high school grades using a Wilcoxon signed-rank test, finding no significant differences. This allowed direct comparisons of attitudes between genders using independent t-tests. Assumptions of normality were checked via the Shapiro–Wilk test and quantile-quantile plots, revealing acceptable normality for motivation and self-efficacy, though appreciation and anxiety deviated slightly but were deemed suitable for t-tests. Variances between groups were equal, as indicated by Levene's test, and while some outliers were present, their influence on results was assessed as minimal. Effect sizes for t-tests were calculated using Cohen's d, interpreted as small (0.2), medium (0.5), or large (0.8).

To assess changes in attitudes throughout the course, we conducted four mixed-design ANOVAs with gender as a between-subjects factor and time (beginning vs. end of course) as a within-subjects factor. Self-efficacy exhibited normally distributed residuals at the end of the course, while the other three attitudes met the criteria for approximate normality despite slight deviations. Homogeneity of variances was confirmed via Levene's test, and covariances were assessed using Box's M-test. Sphericity was tested using Mauchly's test and corrected as needed. Effect sizes were calculated using generalized eta squared, with thresholds for interpretation set at small (0.01), medium (0.06), and large (0.14).

The influence of attitudes on performance was analyzed through binary logistic regression, using achievement in the final course project as the dependent variable. Predictor variables included gender, high school grades, and the pre-course attitudinal measures, as these were unaffected by potential biases introduced during the course. Achievement levels were categorized into high (score of 15) and low (scores of 0, 5, or 10), reflecting differing levels of understanding and ability in writing and interpreting proofs. This categorization yielded balanced group sizes.

Throughout all analyses, statistical significance was determined using the conventional alpha level of 0.05. However, as this study adopted an exploratory approach, p-values up to 0.1 were noted for their potential relevance. No corrections for multiple comparisons were applied to avoid overlooking promising trends (Streiner & Norman, 2011), though care was taken to minimize overinterpretation of marginally significant results. Overall, this approach aimed to balance rigorous analysis with openness to uncovering novel insights for future research.

Attitudinal measures were adapted from the ATMI (Attitudes Toward Mathematics Inventory) and included self-efficacy (e.g., "I am good at writing mathematical proofs"), anxiety (e.g., "Studying proofs makes me feel nervous"), appreciation (e.g., "Studying proofs helps me with problem-solving in other areas"), and motivation (e.g., "The challenge of proving appeals to me"). These items were designed to capture key dimensions of students' experiences with mathematical proof and their potential influence on learning outcomes.

Results

Descriptive statistics

Table 2 presents the means, standard deviations, Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the attitude variables, and Pearson's correlation coefficients between them. Cronbach's alpha assesses the internal consistency of each variable, indicating how closely related the items comprising the variable are. The table also includes data on gender (male/female), high school final exam grades, and performance in the final project (low/high).

Preliminary observations of the means revealed that Self-efficacy increased during the course, rising from 2.70 to 3.01, while Anxiety decreased from 2.43 to 2.25. Appreciation remained consistently high, with a slight increase from 3.87 pre-course to 3.92 post-course. Motivation showed a marginal improvement, increasing from 3.01 to 3.09. Notably, Anxiety displayed the highest variability among participants, with standard deviations of 0.93 (pre-course) and 0.92 (post-course). Motivation had a comparable standard deviation in the post-course survey (0.92). All Cronbach's alpha coefficients exceeded 0.88, signifying strong internal consistency across the attitude variables.

All correlations between the attitude variables were statistically significant ($p < 0.01$). The strongest positive correlations were observed between Motivation and Self-efficacy (0.57 pre-course, 0.66 post-course) and between Motivation and Appreciation (0.59 pre-course, 0.56 post-course). Conversely, the strongest negative correlations involved Anxiety and Self-efficacy (−0.55 pre-course, −0.64 post-course), as well as Anxiety and Motivation (−0.55 pre-course, −0.62 post-course).

	11. Project	10. Gender	9. HS grade	8. Mot (post)	7. App (post)	6. Anx (post)
	-	-	5.56	3.09	3.92	2.25
	-	-	1.25	0.92	0.81	0.92
	-	-	-	0.92	0.91	0.93
	0.19**	0.13*	0.29**	0.74**	0.71**	0.70**
	-0.17**	-0.11	-0.14*	0.66**	0.29**	-0.64**
	0.07	0.11	-0.02	-0.62**	-0.27**	
	0.23**	0.17**	0.21**	0.56**		
	0.28**	0.16**	0.32**			
	-0.27**	-0.08	-0.21**			
	0.08	0.08	0.06			
	0.26**	0.18**	0.20**			
	0.25**	-0.00				
	0.03					

For the attitude variables, correlation is reported within the timing context (pre- or post-course) for different variables, and between the timing contexts for the same variable. Attitude variables range from 1 to 5. Abbreviations: Ef = Self-efficacy, Anx = Anxiety, App = Appreciation, Mot = Motivation, pre = pre-course survey, post = post-course survey, HS grade = High school final exam grade, Project = performance in the course's final project. For correlations, gender is coded 1 = female, 2 = male, final project is coded 1 = low result, 2 = high result. * $p < 0.05$. ** $p < 0.01$.

Table 3: Summary of Linear Regressions for High School Grades Predicting Attitudes Towards Proving

Attitude	Linear coefficient of high school grade			Standardised coefficient	t	p
	b	SE	95% CI			
Self-efficacy	0.17***	0.036	[0.10, 0.25]	0.29	4.89	<0.001
Anxiety	-0.12*	0.045	[-0.20, -0.02]	-0.14	-2.37	0.02
Appreciation	-0.01	0.037	[-0.08, 0.06]	-0.02	-0.31	0.76
Motivation	0.14***	0.040	[0.06, 0.22]	0.21	3.43	<0.001

* $p < 0.05$. ** $p < 0.01$. *** $p < 0.001$

Table 4: Summary of t-test results for the effect of gender on attitudes towards proving

Attitude	Female		Male		t	p	Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD			
Motivation	2.86	0.83	3.14	0.82	-2.14*	0.03	-0.34
Appreciation	3.77	0.73	3.94	0.76	-1.85	0.07	-0.23
Self-efficacy	2.59	0.77	2.79	0.75	-2.76**	0.006	-0.27
Anxiety	2.54	0.90	2.33	0.96	1.82	0.07	0.22

The Welch correction was used to calculate the effective degrees of freedom for all t-tests * $p < 0.05$ ** $p < 0.01$

Differences in high school grades between genders were examined, with no significant differences found ($p = 0.93$). Due to the lack of normal distribution in grades for either gender, as confirmed by the Shapiro–Wilk normality test ($p < 0.001$ for both groups), this non-parametric test was deemed appropriate.

Subsequently, four t-tests were conducted to evaluate gender-based differences in attitudes toward proving. As shown in Table 4, male students demonstrated significantly higher levels of self-efficacy compared to female students ($t(253.0) = -2.76$, $p = 0.006$, with Welch correction). Similarly, male students scored higher on motivation than their female counterparts ($t(252.0) = -2.14$, $p = 0.034$, with Welch correction). In contrast, no significant gender differences were observed in levels of appreciation or anxiety. Effect sizes for the significant differences were small.

Changes in attitudes during the course

To evaluate changes in attitude variables throughout the course for both genders, a mixed-design ANOVA was conducted, incorporating time as a within-subjects factor and gender as a between-subjects factor. The means and standard deviations for these variables at the beginning and end of the course, categorized by gender, are presented in Table 5.

The analysis revealed a significant and substantial increase in self-efficacy during the course, accompanied by a significant reduction in anxiety, with a moderate effect size. Motivation showed a marginally significant increase ($p = 0.051$), though the effect size was small, while appreciation remained unchanged over time. No significant interaction was found between time and gender, indicating that both male and female students exhibited similar trends in the changes of these attitude variables. Table 6 provides a detailed summary of these effects.

Table 5: Means and standard deviations of the attitude variables at the beginning and at the end of the course, broken down by gender

Attitude	Beginning		End					
	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male		
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD		
Motivation	2.86	0.83	3.14	0.82	2.91	0.91	3.24	0.90
Appreciation	3.77	0.73	3.94	0.76	3.85	0.83	3.99	0.80
Self-efficacy	2.59	0.77	2.79	0.75	2.86	0.78	3.13	0.83
Anxiety	2.54	0.89	2.33	0.96	2.33	0.89	2.18	0.94

Table 6: Summary for the mixed-design ANOVA comparing the attitudes towards proving at the beginning and at the end of the course and between genders

predictor	Motivation			Appreciation		
	F(1, 265)	p	η^2g	F(1, 265)	p	η^2g
Time	3.83	0.05	0.002	2.51	0.11	0.001
Gender	9.54**	0.002	0.030	2.98	0.09	0.010
Time×Gender	0.43	0.51	<0.001	0.20	0.66	<0.001
Gender	F(1, 265)	p	η^2g	F(1, 265)	p	η^2g
	62.89***	<0.001	2.036	17.00***	<0.001	0.010
Time×Gender	0.80	0.37	<0.001	0.45	0.50	<0.001

Achievement predicted by prior attitudes, high school grade and gender

To determine the extent to which gender, prior academic performance, and initial attitudes influenced success in the course's final project, a logistic regression analysis was performed. The dependent variable in the model was defined as achieving a "high" score (15) on a discrete scale of 0, 5, 10, and 15. The results are summarized in Table 7.

Among the variables examined, prior high school grades and motivation emerged as the only statistically significant predictors of achievement, controlling for all other factors. For each unit increase in high school grade, the odds of attaining a high score on the final project increased by a factor of 1.5. Similarly, a one-unit increase in motivation raised the likelihood of achieving a high score by a factor of 1.6. Other factors, including gender, self-efficacy, anxiety, and appreciation, showed no significant effect on final project outcomes.

The mean scores in the final project were slightly higher for men (11.0) compared to women (10.6), but this difference was not statistically significant, indicating that motivation and academic preparedness were more critical factors in predicting success than demographic variables or initial attitudes.

Table 7: Binary Logistic Regression Predicting High Achievement in the Final Project of the Course in Terms of Gender, High School Grade, and Attitudes Towards Proving at the Beginning of the Course

Predictor	Coefficient	SE	95% CI	z	OR	p
Gender aa	-0.02	0.20	[-0.41, 0.37]	-0.09	0.98	0.93
High school grade	0.41***	0.10	[0.23, 0.61]	4.32	1.51	<0.001
Motivation	0.47**	0.18	[0.13, 0.82]	2.65	1.60	0.008
Appreciation	-0.19	0.16	[-0.50, 0.12]	-1.19	0.83	0.24
Self-efficacy	0.13	0.17	[-0.21, 0.46]	0.75	1.14	0.46
Anxiety	-0.19	0.14	[-0.47, 0.09]	-1.32		

Notes:

z: Standardized coefficient. OR: Odds ratio.

0 = female, 1 = male.

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Discussion

Beliefs and emotional dispositions play a crucial role in shaping how students approach learning and academic tasks. This research examines the attitudes of first-year university students toward mathematical proving, which is widely acknowledged as one of the most challenging aspects of transitioning to university-level mathematics. The findings indicate that specific attitudinal factors can significantly influence students' performance and are, in turn, shaped by instructional methods and the broader learning environment.

The study also reveals that attitudes toward proving closely resemble general attitudes toward mathematics, particularly in how they differ between genders. Upon entering university, distinct gender-related patterns emerge, with variations in confidence, motivation, and other affective dimensions that influence students' experiences with proving tasks. These insights highlight the importance of understanding and addressing the affective dimensions of learning to support students during this critical academic transition.

Understanding Attitudes Through Assessment

In this study, the variables representing attitudes were not derived from a specific theoretical framework. Instead, they were constructed by adapting and combining elements from pre-existing tools designed to measure attitudes in educational contexts. The study focused on four key variables: self-efficacy, anxiety, appreciation, and motivation. These variables align with well-established constructs in mathematics education. Self-efficacy reflects an individual's belief in their own abilities ("I believe I can"), while appreciation captures the perceived value of the subject being studied ("I think it is useful"). In contrast, anxiety represents a strong emotional reaction, often negative ("I feel repulsed"), and motivation reflects a proactive interest in engaging with proof-related tasks ("I find it interesting").

The instrument demonstrated strong overall performance, successfully differentiating between the four attitudinal dimensions and exhibiting high internal reliability within each. Both self-efficacy and motivation showed distributions close to normal. However, appreciation displayed a ceiling effect, as responses were clustered toward the high end, suggesting overwhelmingly positive perceptions. Similarly, anxiety showed a floor effect, with fewer pronounced responses and a less distinct distribution peak. These limitations indicate areas for improvement if the instrument is to be refined for future research.

There was a relationship between attitudes, previous academic achievements, and gender.

At the start of the course, students displayed varied attitudes toward proving, including differences in self-efficacy, anxiety, and motivation. A positive correlation emerged between high school grades and both self-efficacy and motivation, while anxiety showed a negative correlation. Although proving was not a significant component of Israel high school mathematics, prior academic performance was clearly linked to students' attitudes toward this mathematical process.

These findings align with the hypothesis that self-efficacy is shaped by previous experiences (Bandura, 1997). Similarly, they confirm research showing that high-performing students are more likely to perceive themselves positively as learners of proof compared to their lower-performing peers (Stylianou et al., 2015). Prior studies have also established connections between performance in mathematics and self-efficacy (Hackett & Betz, 1989; Pajares & Graham, 1999), anxiety (Ma & Kishor, 1997; Ho et al., 2000; Miller & Bichsel, 2004), and motivation (Middleton & Spanias, 1999; Murayama et al., 2013; Singh et al., 2002). Unlike these results, appreciation for proof showed limited variability in this sample, differing from findings that higher-performing students tend to value proofs more (Stylianou et al., 2015).

Gender differences in attitudes were also observed. Male students reported significantly higher self-efficacy and motivation than female students, consistent with previous studies documenting lower self-efficacy among

women in mathematics (Betz & Hackett, 1983; Frost et al., 1994; Leder, 1995; Lahdenperä, 2018; Arens et al., 2022). This suggests a similar gap in attitudes toward proving, which aligns with findings that motivation to study mathematics decreases among girls during middle school (Middleton & Spanias, 1999).

In contrast, no significant gender differences were found in appreciation or anxiety toward proving. Previous research has often highlighted gender disparities in mathematics anxiety (Hembree, 1990; Wigfield & Meece, 1988; Devine et al., 2012), but this study identified only a small, non-significant difference, with males showing slightly higher appreciation and lower anxiety. This could reflect limitations in the sensitivity of the measurement instrument or the limited exposure students had to proving at this stage, which might have prevented female students from developing strong negative reactions.

The interaction between the educational setting and students' attitudes

During the course, students demonstrated an overall increase in self-efficacy and a reduction in anxiety. Motivation and appreciation also showed some improvement, although these changes were not statistically significant. Since no control group was included and many students were concurrently enrolled in other proof-based courses, it cannot be definitively concluded that the observed changes were solely attributable to this specific course. Nonetheless, given that proving is rarely addressed outside mathematics, and that this course was explicitly designed as an introduction to proving, it is plausible that aspects of the learning environment contributed to these changes.

The increase in self-efficacy aligns with established frameworks emphasizing the importance of prior achievements, observational learning, and positive reinforcement (e.g., Bandura, 1997). Scaffolded tasks of increasing complexity may have allowed students to build confidence through early successes, enhancing their self-belief in tackling proof tasks (Selden & Selden, 2013). Supportive and constructive feedback from instructors further reinforced these gains, while opportunities to engage in peer review provided a comparative context for self-assessment. Additionally, the instructor's emphasis on normalizing mistakes as part of the proving process likely reduced anxiety and fostered a more positive learning experience (Supekar et al., 2015).

In the final project, motivation at the start of the course emerged as a strong predictor of performance, even after controlling for prior skills and other attitude variables. This contrasts with earlier studies linking self-efficacy and anxiety to academic outcomes (e.g., Pajares & Graham, 1999; Ma & Kishor, 1997; Ho et al., 2000; Miller & Bichsel, 2004), where such factors often play a significant role. One explanation for this discrepancy may be the analytical control for initial performance, which could have masked the effects of self-efficacy and anxiety if these were already tied to pre-existing competencies. Furthermore, high intercorrelation among the attitude variables introduces potential challenges of multicollinearity, complicating their independent effects.

Motivation was particularly notable in enabling students to exceed their prior skill levels during the final project. The extended timeframe for completing the project, combined with the ongoing support from instructors, likely allowed highly motivated students to dedicate greater effort and achieve superior outcomes. This underscores the critical role of motivation in driving persistence and engagement, particularly in tasks requiring sustained focus and independent problem-solving.

Suggestions for Future Research and Educational Practice

The findings from this study indicate that students' attitudes toward proving play a crucial role in their performance on certain types of proving tasks and can evolve positively over time. This underscores the importance of incorporating attitudes into the design of teaching methods and assessment strategies. The instrument developed for this research offers a robust quantitative framework for evaluating students' attitudes and holds promise for further refinement and application in future studies, particularly if it is aligned with well-established theoretical models, such as those proposed by Di Martino and Zan (2010).

An increase in self-efficacy and a decrease in anxiety were observed among students during the course, suggesting that supportive and collaborative learning environments can foster positive shifts in attitudes. For instance, creating a safe space for students to engage with their peers and instructors, discussing factors that might provoke anxiety, and encouraging the sharing of incomplete ideas can contribute to an atmosphere conducive to growth. To deepen the understanding of these changes, future research could include qualitative approaches, such as interviews and classroom observations.

The results also highlight a persistent gender gap in attitudes toward proving, with female students showing less favorable dispositions compared to their male counterparts. This aligns with broader patterns in mathematics education, where systemic inequities often disadvantage female students. Addressing these disparities requires deliberate action from educators, including the adoption of student-centered pedagogical strategies, as research suggests such approaches can narrow the gap between genders (Lahdenperä, 2018; Laursen et al., 2014). However, care must be taken to account for the impact of cultural narratives that can undermine female students' participation and engagement in mathematical activities, as highlighted by Reinholz et al. (2022). By challenging these systemic barriers and creating equitable learning environments, educators can better support all students in developing confidence and competence in proving.

Appendix

The results of the factor loadings for each item in both the pre- and post-course surveys are summarized in Table 8. The items are categorized based on their source: PSE items originate from the PSE instrument, which assesses self-efficacy, while the other items are derived from the ATMI instrument. Within the ATMI framework, SEC represents “sense of security,” VAL stands for “value,” ENJ captures “enjoyment,” and MOT refers to “motivation.”

Table 8: Factor loadings in pre- and post-course surveys

Item	Pre-course loadings				Post-course loadings			
	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4
PSE4	0.88	0.03	-0.03	0.00	0.90	-0.05	-0.01	-0.03
SEC13	0.86	-0.03	0.00	-0.03	0.80	-0.02	-0.04	0.12
PSE5	0.77	0.05	0.07	-0.01	0.76	0.05	0.10	-0.05
SEC2	0.73	-0.15	-0.01	-0.08	0.73	-0.16	0.02	-0.06
PSE2	0.68	0.08	-0.01	0.06	0.56	0.12	-0.02	0.27
SEC11	0.73	-0.09	0.03	0.01	0.74	-0.11	-0.01	0.00
SEC12	0.03	0.92	-0.04	0.09	0.02	0.89	0.06	-0.03
SEC6	0.03	0.86	0.03	-0.07	0.10	0.89	0.01	-0.11
SEC3	-0.08	0.80	-0.01	0.07	-0.05	0.84	-0.05	0.09
SEC5	0.02	0.76	0.00	0.01	-0.08	0.76	-0.01	0.05
SEC4	-0.12	0.74	0.07	0.03	-0.09	0.80	-0.01	0.10
SEC1	0.10	0.68	-0.05	-0.20	0.04	0.64	0.03	-0.33
VAL10	0.06	0.03	0.91	-0.12	0.04	0.02	0.91	-0.07
VAL7	0.04	-0.01	0.83	-0.10	0.03	0.01	0.86	-0.07
VAL8	0.01	-0.01	0.78	0.04	-0.08	-0.07	0.75	0.15
VAL2	-0.07	-0.06	0.74	0.05	0.04	0.03	0.81	0.01
VAL4	-0.04	0.03	0.66	0.19	-0.01	0.00	0.60	0.21
VAL6	0.03	0.02	0.70	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.81	-0.10
MOT3	-0.19	-0.01	0.00	0.94	-0.04	-0.02	0.15	0.73
ENJ4	0.13	-0.02	-0.04	0.80	0.08	-0.05	0.04	0.77
ENJ6	-0.09	-0.01	0.20	0.73	-0.09	-0.01	0.23	0.75
MOT2	0.03	0.04	0.06	0.65	0.02	0.03	-0.06	0.83
ENJ5	0.16	0.00	-0.07	0.53	0.15	0.04	-0.10	0.69
ENJ1	0.25	-0.07	0.02	0.52	0.12	-0.10	-0.02	0.73

The items are grouped according to the factors on which they loaded most strongly. Loadings above 0.5 are emphasized with boldface.

Table 9 provides a detailed list of the question items included in the final factor analysis solution. For clarity, all items have been translated from the original Israel. These tables offer insights into how the survey items align with the intended constructs and how the responses evolved over the duration of the course.

Table 9: Question items retained after factor analysis, translated from Israel

Factor	Question Item
Self-Efficacy	SEC2: I am able to do proofs without too much difficulty
	SEC11: I learn proving easily
	SEC13: I believe I am good at solving proof problems
	PSE2: I can often come up with my own proofs for statements I see in a lecture or class
	PSE4: I am good at writing mathematical proofs
Anxiety	PSE5: It is easy for me to come up with convincing and logically sound mathematical arguments
	SEC1: When I hear the word “proof,” I get a feeling of dislike
	SEC3: It makes me nervous to even think about having to do a proof-related problem
	SEC4: I am always under a terrible strain when working on proofs
	SEC5: My mind goes blank and I am unable to think clearly when working on proofs
	SEC6: Proofs make me uncomfortable

Factor	Question Item
Appreciation	SEC12: Studying proofs makes me feel nervous
	VAL2: Studying proving is useful regardless of my field of study
	VAL4: Studying proving is important and valuable
	VAL6: Strong proving skills could help me in my career
	VAL7: Proving is important for people besides mathematicians
	VAL8: I think studying challenging proofs is useful
Motivation	VAL10: I believe studying proving will help me with problem solving in other fields
	ENJ1: I really like proving
	ENJ4: I like solving new proof-related problems
	ENJ5: I would prefer to do a proof problem than a problem related to another topic
	ENJ6: Studying proving is very interesting
	MOT2: I am willing to do extra proof problems
	MOT3: I find the challenge of proving fascinating

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